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Research Data Scary Tales

Biodiversity Edition

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Introduction

Small mistakes can have serious consequences. You can lose a day or a decade of work or your data may be lost forever. With our selection of scientific horror stories, we illustrate common and sometimes fatal mistakes in research data management – and how they may have been prevented. In this, we follow the fine example of the Thuringian Competence Network for Research Data Management (TKFDM), who compiled a wonderful collection of [Research Data Scary Tales](#)¹. However, working with biodiversity data comes with some particular pitfalls. So join us in being creeped out with us by common mishaps and malicious hidden agendas... Can you guess what went wrong?

All of our stories are available in the [NFDI4Biodiversity Knowledge Base](#) – consisting of the puzzle phrase, illustration, solution, suggestions for better research data management, and sources.

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Table of contents

1. Completely out of place	3
2. Web of lies.....	4
3. 3, 2, 1... no picture for you today	5
4. From head to toe, crown to sole	6

¹ Lang, K., Gerlach, R., Rex, J., Neute, N., Annett Schröter, Schwartze, V., Assmann, C., Lehmann, A., Boelter, S., & Meyer, R. (2023). Research Data ScaryTales (4.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10281701>

1. Completely out of place

Because he had slipped in the line, she couldn't come to any reasonable conclusion.

A student was asked to analyze data for a term paper. She had received the data from her lecturer. It included study areas, plant species, species names and the frequency of animals found on the plants. The student then added information from the literature on the degree of specialization and other species characteristics for each of these animal species. The analysis revealed that none of the expected correlations could be found – the specialists were not very specialized, and some usually common species turned out to be very rare. Despite different methods of analysis, the results remained the same: neither the different plant species nor the study areas differed in the composition of the animal species.

Shortly before the work had to be handed in, it turned out that the species names in the table had slipped by two lines. Consequently, the connection between species and their locations and frequency had been broken. It was no longer possible to reconstruct exactly how and when the error had occurred, but the student had received the data in an already corrupted state and had worked with the incorrect data set from the outset. No further analysis could be conducted before the assignment was due, so her work was accepted despite being based on flawed data. After all, she had carried out all the required analyses and bravely discussed the (very unsatisfactory) results-

Such errors are unfortunately quite common, especially when data is saved and edited exclusively in spreadsheet programs such as Excel or LibreOffice. It is therefore very important to work exclusively with copies of the raw data, but never in the raw data itself. If data is to be re-sorted, selected or aggregated, programs such as OpenRefine, queries in relational databases (e.g. MariaDB, SQLite) or the use of R or Python scripts are recommended.

Source: Personal communication.

2. Web of lies

They trusted him blindly and had to bear the consequences.

A scientist studied the behaviour of spiders and of social insects. His research was ground-breaking and he made a quick career. He cooperated with many researchers to analyse his experiments, and together they published many highly cited scientific articles. Then doubts came up about his results. When some of his co-authors checked his raw data more thoroughly, they came across inconsistencies, for example identical data for different individuals. Further, he was unable to explain where the individuals that he used in experiments came from or which individuals were actually used (Kozlov 2022). And there was more suspicious data in other articles: After a thorough examination, more than a dozen of his scientific articles had to be retracted. A multi-year investigation came to the conclusion that he had deliberately falsified or fabricated data. As a result, he lost his position.

But he was not the only one who had to bear the consequences: more than 50 of his co-authors of the retracted articles were affected by the fallout. Among them were many doctoral students and early career researchers (López Lloreda 2023). Many never considered to question the data of their supervisor or of the collaborator of their supervisor. Some had to postpone their doctoral graduation, others had problems finding a job, and all of them had to regain the trust of their collaborators. Finally, substantial sums of research funding were spent on replicating supposedly spectacular findings – which unsurprisingly did not work.

The case raised awareness of the importance to critically check raw data of spectacular analyses in each and every case both among scientific journals and many researchers. Today, it is common practise that it is not only required for authors to submit their manuscript to a journal, but to also make their raw data accessible for reviewers, before they can publish a scientific article. Furthermore, there is an increasing number of researchers trying to prevent similar cases in the future by practising Open Science: the "Society for Open, Reliable, and Transparent Ecology and Evolutionary Biology" (SORTEE) is a global network of scientists and students who promote Open Science in ecology and evolutionary biology. Generally, this much can be said: extraordinary statements require extraordinarily good data to support them.

Sources:

Kozlov, M. (2022). How a scandal in spider biology upended researchers' lives. *Nature*, 608(7924), 658–659. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-02156-2>

López Lloreda, C. (2023). *University investigation found prominent spider biologist fabricated, falsified data*. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adi6906>

SORTEE. *Society for Open, Reliable, and Transparent Ecology and Evolutionary Biology (SORTEE)*. <https://www.sortee.org>

3. 3, 2, 1... no picture for you today

Although he had everything with him, he couldn't work.

As part of an experiment on the colonization of new habitats by marine, sessile species, photos of settlement plates were taken regularly over several months. These photos were used for species identification and the analysis of settlement patterns. However, the settlement plates were installed on artificial islands in the Wadden Sea, which made sampling particularly challenging. Each sampling session, and therefore each opportunity for photo documentation, was only possible on a few days each month and required a full day of effort due to the time-intensive journey.

One day, however, the doctoral student made a critical mistake: he forgot to clear the camera's memory card and back up the data before heading out. He only realized the problem when he was already out at sea—far from any internet connection and without any way to secure the files elsewhere. Deleting some redundant photos provided only limited additional storage, calling for an extra sampling day. Aside from the time loss, the altered schedule also made subsequent analysis more complex.

The lesson from this incident was clear: regular back-ups are essential! 3...2...1 – Backup: at least three copies of the data, on at least two different storage media, with at least one stored at an external location. If the doctoral student had followed this rule, he could have avoided an additional day of work – and a lot of frustration.

Source: Personal communication

4. From head to toe, crown to sole

Although all measurements were available, analysis had to wait for a long time.

A doctoral student was given a data set for analysis that contained measurements of different plants. A former member of the research group had examined several individuals per species for this data. Several distances were measured on each specimen. A little hand drawn sketch indicated from where to where each measurement was supposed to be conducted. In this sketch, each distance was labelled with a different character, which were then used as column names in the measuring sheet.

Unfortunately, the sketch was lost – and with it the information which character represented which distance. Under these circumstances, an analysis was rendered impossible. Only after months of searching, the measuring protocol could be reconstructed.

In order to be able to use data as long as possible, comprehensive metadata are essential. In this case, a first step would have been to use „speaking“ column names (leaf length, leaf area, seed mass) and units (mm, cm², mg) for each measurement. Detailed descriptions of each measurement would have been even better, maybe referring to a corresponding figure (e.g. „leaf width: maximum width of the leaf orthogonal to maximum leaf length“, „maximum shoot height“, „leaf area: leaves were scanned and areas were calculated automatically in ImageJ“). Well-documented data facilitate your own analyses and they are available long term – for your own research questions and for those of others. Finally, generally standardised measuring protocols and standardised vocabularies or ontologies with defined terms (GFBio 2024, Kissling et al. 2018) allow for using data in global analyses, like e.g. the modelling of biodiversity trends by IPBES.

Sources: Personal communication

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IPBES. (2024). *Intergovernmental Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES)*. <https://www.ipbes.net>

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